

**Bank Guarantees on Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions:
Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer
Bibliometrics**

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around Bank Guarantees using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key word “Bank Guarantee” within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank Guarantees based on the journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 21 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Guarantees in Sharia and Conventional Banking. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding Bank Guarantees, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Bank Guarantee; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

Introduction

At the beginning of the era of globalization, entrepreneurs competed with intense competition to promote their own businesses. They not only need laws that guarantee legal certainty for their businesses, but also need financial institutions such as banks that can ensure the smooth running of their businesses. One way that is often done is by using banking products in the form of bank guarantees.

In Sharia Financial Institutions, bank guarantees are usually referred to as kafalah. Kafalah is a sharia banking service product which aims to provide guarantees to third parties to fulfill the obligations of the insured party if the insured party experiences default. Providing a bank guarantee as a guarantee is in accordance with Islamic law. The Koran and Hadith allow humans to help each other in the form of guarantees.

Bank guarantee is a product offered by banks. A bank guarantee is a payment guarantee provided by a bank in the form of a written letter addressed to a particular individual, company or legal entity. The basis of a bank guarantee is guarantee (borgtocht) which is regulated in Articles 1820-1850 of the Civil Code. Bank guarantee institutions have been known for a long time, but their use still needs to be improved. Bank guarantee facilities are a reliable and safe option for guarantors and guaranteed parties.

Scientific publications about bank guarantees are increasing from year to year according to search results on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). From 2012 to 2021, 44 studies were recorded on bank guarantee contracts. This shows that bank guarantee contracts are one of the sharia products that are popular among the public. Based on this background, this research is important to determine the impact of bank guarantees on Sharia Financial Institutions and improve the community's economy.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank Guarantee use library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank Guarantees, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is mapping research topics surrounding Bank Guarantees, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Bank Guarantee is a form of guarantee where the bank acts as the guarantor for the customer (guarantee applicant) to the guarantor for transactions carried out by both parties, if the customer is later unable to pay off his obligations due to problems. A bank guarantee is a written contract at the request of a customer (guaranteed) to cover certain securities as a form of compensation that arises if the guarantor does not fulfill his obligations to the bank.

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications.

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology.

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The object of the research is Bank Guarantees in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank Guarantees originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword “Bank Guarantee” for the entire year (2012-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the

number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research.

Results and Discussion

This chapter discusses research mapping around Bank Guarantees in Sharia Financial Institutions using VOSviewer bibliometric studies and Library Researchs. The results obtained from the Garuda website (Garba Rujukan Digital) were 44 publication titles in the form of articles originating from accredited national journals.

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank Guarantees in Sharia and Conventional Financial Institutions

The results of the analysis of scientific publications regarding Bank Guarantees during the period 2012 to 2022 show an increase and decrease in the number of publications each year. It was recorded that in 2019 and 2021 there were 8 articles published. Therefore, the average scientific publication regarding Bank Guarantees is 4 articles per year.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding Bank Guarantees by year

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2012	1	2016	4	2020	8
2013	5	2017	7	2021	2
2014	4	2018	3	2022	1
2015	1	2019	8		
Total 44					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 2 affiliates/institutions that publish the most research articles about Bank Guarantees in Sharia Financial Institutions. The Civil Law Science Journal is the journal publisher that publishes the most research results regarding bank guarantees, with a total of 3 articles.

Table 2. Ranking of institutions and journals publishing scientific publications regarding Bank Guarantees

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Scientific Journal for Civil Law	3
Dedication of Student Journal, Journal of law (legal science journal), Kertha Semaya: Legal Science Journal, Lex Jurnalica (Legal Science)	2
AGHNIYA: Journal of Islamic Economics, BANCO: Journal of Sharia Management and Banking, Civil Law, Dialogi Iuridica, Legal Dynamics, Dinar: Journal of Economic Study Programs, IJTIHAD, Inovbiz: Journal of Business Innovation, Journal Equitable, Journal Industrial Services, Jurist-diction, Jurnal Al-Muqaranah: Journal of the Comparative School of Study	1

Program, Cakrawala Hukum Journal, IUS Journal of Law and Justice Studies, Justisia Journal: Journal of Law, Legislation and Social Institutions, Litigation Journal (e-journal), Student Online Journal (JOM) in the Field of Science Law, Journal of Accounting and Financial Education, Catalog, Krisna Law: Student Journal of the Faculty of Law, Krisnadwipayana University, Legal Opinion, Lex Administratum, Lex Crimen, Lex Librium: Journal of Legal Studies, Lex Privatum, Menara Riau: Journal of Science and Development of Islamic Society, Notarius, PALAR: (Pakuan Law Review), Perspective, Serat Acitya, Share: Journal of Islamic Economics and Finance, Sriwijaya Law Review, Yustisia J.

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 3, of the total of 44 research publication articles regarding Bank Guarantees in Sharia Financial Institutions contained on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba), the most productive researchers are Toni Butar Butar (Esa Unggul University) and Khairani (Syiah Kuala University), respectively - Each wrote 2 articles.

Table 3. Ranking of the most productive researchers

Researcher	Number of Publications
Toni Butar Butar (Esa Unggul University), Khairani (Syiah Kuala University)	2
Riska Agustina, Grace Sharon, Hartono Widodo (Krisnadwipayana University), Sri Retno Widyorini (UNTAG Semarang), Ichsan Ahmad Windardi (Airlangga University), Ni Putu Purnama Andari, Ida Bagus Putra Atmadja, I Nyoman Bagiastara, Putu Novi Pujayanti, Ida Bagus Putu Sutama (Udayana University), Arafat, Lily Erlianti, Muhammad Ali Husni, Kornelis, M Kurniawan (University 17 August 1945 Samarinda), Desy Nurkristia Tejawati (Wijaya Kusuma University Surabaya), Tjiangdi (Slamet Riyadi University), Kapugu Betsy, Denish Davied Dariwu, Daniel Easter Matasik, Sarah D. L Roeroe (Sam Ratulangi University), Erens Corneles, Yuliandari Lela, Sirang (Tadulako University), Deryan, Auzan Qasthary, Sri Walny Rahayu, Rinaldi (Syiah Kuala University), Kennie Dhillon (University of North Sumatra), Firdaus, Yosi Mandalagi, Haniva Rahmadani, Ulfia Hasanah (Riau University), Erma Defiana Putrayanti (National University), Ade Hari Siswanto (Esa Unggul University), Sugiyanto (Indonesian Cooperative Management Institute), Errizka, Fitriamadewi Bey (Diponegoro University), Rineke Sara (Borobudur University), Suwardi Gunawan, Deasy Kartika Rahayu Kuncoro, Ario Sambodo (Mulawarman University), Johan Wahyu Wicaksono (Luqman Al-Hakim Islamic College), Prama Widayat (Lancang Kuning University), Hamdani (UIN Ar-Raniry Banda Aceh), M Yadi Harahap (UIN North Sumatra), Muttatoh Hirin (UIN Sultan Syarif Kasim Riau), Suwandi Kusnaedi, Zainal Said, Muhammad Kamal Zubair (IAIN Parepare), Rahayu Hartini (Muhammadiyah)	1

University of Malang), Rahmayati (Muhammadiyah University of North Sumatra), Yohannes Ibrahim, Yohanes Hermanto Sirait (Maranatha Christian University), Candra Irawan, Emelia Kontesa, I Gusti Yesi Triastiti (Bengkulu University), Kurnianingsih, Gandhi Pharmacist (Pasundan University Bandung), Diman Ade Mulada (Mataram University), Iman Nur Hidayat (Darussalam Gontor University), Rahel Octora (Maranatha Christian University), Youngky Yudho Pramono (Brawijaya University).

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping Research on Bank Guarantees in Sharia Financial Institutions

Search results for research articles via the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are stored in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, then entered and described using VOSViewer with the following results:

Figure 1. Network visualization of research development maps regarding Bank Guarantees

Source: Processed data, VOSViewer 1.6.18 software.

the co-word map and the growth of research regarding Bank Guarantees in Sharia Financial Institutions is broken down into 7 clusters and 107 topics, namely as follows:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 25 topics, namely: abstract factor, auction receivables affairs agency, bad credit, billing, bupln, character, situation, coercion, completion, credit, debtor, district court, education, external factor, factor, financial difficulty, force, foreclosure, legal channel, low level, misuse, peace, reach ability, state, unstable economy party regional development bank Samarinda.
- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 20 topics, namely: acceptance, approval, bank guarantee claim, business, business unit, capital, community, credit agreement, development, empirical research, entrepreneur, bank, law, owner, personal guarantee, principal agreement, request, responsibility, umkm, writing.

- Cluster 3. The dark blue color consists of 23 topics, namely: applicant, bank guarantee disbursement, bank guarantee statement, bank guarantor, business actor, cooperation agreement, disbursement, excuse, bank guarantor, holder, civil code, lawsuit, legal conflict, legal procedure, legal remedy, refusal.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 14 topics, namely: authority, bank loan, bankruptcy, representative, curator, decree, hiring decree, general collateral, impact, legal certainty, legal status, object, paragraph.
- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 12 topics, namely: accumulation, administrative costs, banking, costs, guarantee service, Islamic bank, kafalah, performance, regulation, rule, system, thing.
- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 12 topics, namely: analysis, state-owned company, checking, determination, influence, legal protection, Library Research, loss, observation, operating profit, risk, writer.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 5 topics, namely: BSM, construction sector, counter guarantee, financing, kafalah concept.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank Guarantees in Sharia and Conventional Banking

Library Research in previous research journals, researchers found 21 research topics regarding Bank Guarantees in Sharia and Conventional Banking, namely:

First, bank guarantees in banking law, civil law, DSN-MUI fatwa, and Muamalah Fiqh.

Second, the legal aspect of the bank guarantee institution.

Third, collateral for deposits in the bank guarantee agreement.

Fourth, the role of bank guarantees: (1) Between the government and contractors. (2) Protection of consumer rights.

Fifth, issuing a bank guarantee according to the law. 10 of 1998, Presidential Decree no. 95 of 2007, and juridical aspects.

Sixth, obstacles and solutions in implementing bank guarantees.

Seventh, the position of the bank in providing bank guarantees.

Eighth, the role of the bank issuing the bank guarantee as a guarantor for third parties.

Ninth, bank guarantee as a transfer of obligations for customer default according to Civil Code articles 1831 and 1832.

Tenth, criminal aspects regarding the implementation of PT bank guarantees. Bank Ekonomi Raharja KC Semarang according to Law no. 10 of 1998 and BI Decree No. 23 of 1991.

Eleventh, civil liability for bank guarantee claims issued.

Twelfth, legal characteristics of guarantees.

Thirteenth, implementation of risk management and mitigation in bank guarantee products.

Fourteenth, providing financing credit in the form of a bank guarantee.

Fifteenth, the effect of bank guarantee income on operational profit.

Sixteenth, implementation of bank guarantees at Bank Aceh Syariah, Bank Danamon, Bank Negara Indonesia/BNI, Bank Central Asia, Bank Rakyat Indonesia/BRI, Bank Mandiri, Bank Syariah Bukopin, Bank Nagari, Bank Muamalat Indonesia, and Bank Victoria Syariah.

Seventeenth, legal protection for recipients of bank guarantees is provided the bank providing the bank guarantee goes bankrupt.

Eighteenth, application of the Kafalah contract to bank guarantee services.

Nineteenth, implementation of the bank guarantee policy for customs activities based on the Indonesian legal system.

Twentieth, the position of the bank guarantee claimed by the recipient of the guarantee when the debtor is terminated by PKPU by the court.

Twenty-first, legal protection for debtors in standard bank guarantee contracts.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 21 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank Guarantees in Sharia and Conventional Banking.

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